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MUCORMYCOSIS: AN OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Mucormycosis is termed as an angio-invasive fungal infection, connected with high morbidity and mortality. An alteration in the epidemiology of mucormycosis has been discovered in recent years with the rise in frequency, newfound causative agents and susceptible population. The rise has been perceived globally, but it is very advanced in the Asian continent. Though diabetes mellitus surpass all other risk factors in Asia. Post-tuberculosis and chronic renal failure have appeared as a new risk groups. The rhino cerebral mucormycosis is most usually seen in patients with diabetes mellitus. Although considered to be a infrequent infection, mucormycosis (zygomycosis) has emerged as the second most common invasive mould infection. Despite the advent of newer fungicidal agents, mortality rate of mucormycosis resides exceedingly higher. Successful direction of mucormycosis requires early identification, reversal of underlying predisposing risk number, surgical debridement and prompt administration of active antifungal agents. However, mucormycosis is not always amenable to cure. There are challenging obstacles that lead to exertion in management of Amphotericin B. These include unique host-based risk factors for mucormycosis, the fungus' resistance to innate hostdefences and distinctive features of its immunopathogenesis, such as extensive angioinvasion, increased virulence and use of chelators by the fungus as siderophores.

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INTRODUCTION

Mucormycosis (Zygomycosis) is caused by fungi from the Mucorales order. Is also known as Black Fungus. Inhalation of sporangiospores, consumption of tainted food, or traumatic inoculation are the most common ways for humans to become infected. Mucorales fungi are widespread, and their hyphae appear to be broad, aseptate, or coarsely septate ribbon-like hyphae. Mucorales has eleven genera and 27 species that are linked to human illnesses. The most common cause of mucormycosis is *Rhizopus arrhizus*, which is followed by *Apophysomyces*, *Lichtheimia*, *Rhizomucor*, *Mucor*, and *Cunninghamella* species. Between the Western world and Asian countries, there has been a change in the predominance of risk factors/underlying illness and mucormycosis causative agents. In Asia, diabetes mellitus is the most common risk factor, while in Europe and the United States, haematological malignancies and transplantation are substantial risk factors. In healthy people, a large proportion of cases are reported after a traumatic event. Health-care related to mucormycosis has become increasingly reported in recent years. Health-care related to mucormycosis has become increasingly reported in recent years. The current study examines the global incidence of mucormycosis as a function of changes in epidemiological characteristics such as risk factors, causative agents, and underlying disease. [1-12]

TYPES OF MUCORMYCOSIS

Invasive mucormycosis is divided into one of six major clinical forms based on its clinical presentation and anatomic location:

- (1) Rhinocerebral Mucormycosis
- (2) Pulmonary Mucormycosis
- (3) Cutaneous Mucormycosis
- (4) Gastrointestinal Mucormycosis
- (5) Disseminated Mucormycosis
- (6) Endocarditis, osteomyelitis, peritonitis, and kidney infection are uncommon rare types. [13–15]

RHINOCEREBRAL MUCORMYCOSIS

The most frequent type of Mucormycosis is Rhinocerebral Mucormycosis (ROCM), which is primarily encountered in people with Diabetes Mellitus. Patients with underlying malignancies, recipients of solid organ transplants or haematopoietic stem cell transplants, and people with other risk factors are all at risk. Inhalation of fungal sporangiospores in the paranasal sinuses causes this fungus to grow. The infection can quickly spread to nearby tissues. When the invading fungus germinates, it might spread inferiorly to the palate, posteriorly to the sphenoid sinus, laterally in the cavernous sinus to the orbits, or cranially to the brain. The fungus kills the host by attacking the cranium through the orbital apex or cribriform plate of the ethmoid bone. However, imaging tests are nonspecific for ROCM, and histological confirmation of fungal tissue invasion is always required to diagnose ROCM. Given the rapid progression of ROCM and the significant increase in death rate when the fungus penetrates the cranium, every diabetic patient with a headache and visual abnormalities should be evaluated as soon as possible with imaging studies and nasal endoscopy to rule out mucormycosis. [16-19]

PULMONARY MUCORMYCOSIS

Pulmonary mucormycosis is particularly common in neutropenic cancer patients receiving induction chemotherapy and those who have had HSCT and developed graft-versus-host disease. Patients with pulmonary mucormycosis have a high overall mortality rate (76%) that is significantly higher in critically immunocompromised patients. Pulmonary mucormycosis has nonspecific clinical characteristics that are difficult to distinguish from pulmonary aspergillosis. Patients frequently have a high-grade fever (38°C) that does not respond to broad-spectrum medications. Hemoptysis, pleuritic chest pain, and dyspnea are the most prevalent symptoms, while hemoptysis, pleuritic chest pain, and dyspnea are less prevalent. Pulmonary mucormycosis can show as an endobronchial or tracheal lesion in rare cases, especially in diabetics. Endobronchial mucormycosis can produce an obstruction in the airway, resulting in lung collapse, as well as invasion of the hilar blood vessels, culminating in significant hemoptysis. Pulmonary mucormycosis can affect the mediastinum, pericardium, and chest wall, as well as the lungs. On chest imaging, the symptoms of pulmonary mucormycosis are nonspecific and distinct from those of pulmonary aspergillosis. Consolidation, infiltration, nodules, cavitations, atelectasis, effusion, posterior tracheal band thickening, hilar or mediastinal lymphadenopathy, and even normal findings are the most common results. [20–28].

CUTANEOUS MUCORMYCOSIS

Direct immunisation of fungal spores in the skin causes cutaneous mucormycosis (Zygomycosis), which can progress to widespread illness. The opposite (distribution of blood from internal organs to the skin) is extremely uncommon. Only 6 examples were identified by Roden et al as having an inverted distribution (3%). cutaneous mucormycosis is characterised as localised when it affects only the skin or subcutaneous tissue, deep extension when it attacks muscle, tendons, or bone, and circularise when it affects other noncontiguous organs, depending on the severity of the illness. The clinical signs and symptoms of cutaneous mucormycosis differ. A necrotic eschar with surrounding induration and erythema is the typical presentation (demonstration) of cutaneous Zygomycosis. A nonspecific erythematous macule, on the other hand, may represent the cutaneous manifestation of widespread disease in an immunocompromised patient, despite its tiny size and apparent insignificance. When cutaneous mucormycosis is accompanied by necrotic eschars, the lesions can resemble bacterial synergistic gangrene, pyoderma gangrenosum, or other bacterial or fungal infections. [29-35].

Image- Cutaneous Mucormycosis

GASTROINTESTINAL MUCORMYCOSIS

In surviving patients, gastrointestinal mucormycosis is both uncommon and common. In such circumstances, diagnosis can take a long time, and the mortality rate can be as high as 85%. Only 25% of gastrointestinal mucormycosis cases are detected antemortem, and the condition has been linked to preterm neonates, HMs, malnourished children, diabetes mellitus, and a history of corticosteroid usage, according to reports. Consumption of pathogens in foods such as fermented milk and dried bread items causes GI mucormycosis. Gastric mucormycosis may be exacerbated by the consumption of fermented porridges and alcoholic beverages made from corn. Finally, in a hematology-oncology clinic, one group of sources reported on a series of instances of gastrointestinal mucormycosis thought to have been transmitted orally by sporangiospore-infected tongue depressors used for oropharyngeal examinations. Mucormycosis of the gastrointestinal tract can affect any portion of the digestive system, although the stomach is the most commonly afflicted, followed by the colon and ileum.

The infection usually manifests as a cecal, appendiceal, or ileac mass, as well as a gastric perforation, which is typically accompanied by severe upper gastrointestinal tract bleeding. Neutropenic fever, typhilitis, and hematochezia are among conditions that can affect neutropenic patients. Because of the generic nature of gastrointestinal mucormycosis, diagnosis is generally delayed, requiring a high level of suspicion and prompting the use of endoscopic biopsy analysis. Mucormycosis of the gastrointestinal tract can potentially affect the liver, spleen, and pancreas. The fungus can induce peritonitis, bowel perforation, sepsis, and extensive gastrointestinal haemorrhage, which is the leading cause of death. [1],[36-52].

Image- Gastrointestinal Mucormycosis.

DISSEMINATED MUCORMYCOSIS

Mucormycosis in one organ can spread to other organs hematogenously. The lung is the organ most usually associated with dispersion. Dissemination can also happen through the gastrointestinal tract, severe skin lesions, or burns. Although the brain is a common location of spread, lesions in the liver, spleen, heart, and other organs can also be discovered. Patients with high iron levels (particularly those on deferoxamine), severe immunosuppression (e.g., allogeneic stem cell transplant recipients with graft-versus-host disease treated with corticosteroids), or profound neutropenia and active leukaemia are all at risk for disseminated mucormycosis. The host, as well as the location and degree of vascular invasion and tissue infarction in the affected organs, influence the symptoms and progression of disseminated mucormycosis. To change early diagnosis, the varied depiction of disseminated mucormycosis necessitates a high index of suspicion. Disseminated mucormycosis is frequently diagnosed postmortem. Early detection relies heavily on the presence of a metastatic skin lesion. Disseminated mucormycosis is invariably lethal if not treated properly. [53-62]

UNCOMMON FORMS OF MUCORMYCOSIS

Endocarditis, osteomyelitis, peritonitis, and pyelonephritis are some less common or different localised types of mucormycosis. Mucormycosis is a relatively uncommon cause of prosthetic or native valve endocarditis. The most common risk factor is intravenous drug usage. Endocarditis is a type of infection that develops on or around prosthetic valves and can lead to aortic thrombosis. Surgical intervention (e.g., tibial pin placement, anterior cruciate ligament repair) or traumatic inoculation are the most common causes of osteomyelitis. The tibia, calcaneus, femur, cuboid, humerus, scapula, metacarpals, phalanges, and sternum have all been recorded to develop osteomyelitis. Hematogenous osteomyelitis is quite uncommon. Zygomycetes' involvement in the peritoneal cavity in individuals undergoing continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis is also uncommon. Peritonitis is a slow-progressing infection, but the attributable death rate in individuals who get delayed or improper treatment has reached as high as 60%. In all cases of catheter-related mucormycosis, the catheter should be removed as soon as possible, and systemic antifungal medication should be used for many weeks. [58,59,6381]

ETIOLOGY

Mucormycosis is a fungal infection caused by certain moulds. Mucormycetes are the scientific name for these moulds. They can be found/discovered in the soil and decaying organic materials, such as rotting plant, and can be found/discovered all over nature (ubiquitous). Despite the fact that they are commonly found in nature, these moulds rarely create difficulties. They can, however, cause serious, even life-threatening illness in people who have a weaker or compromised immune system. To the highest degree most people develop this infection by breathing in mold spores. Infection can spread more rarely when spores enter the body through a cut or open wound. There are certain persons who are more susceptible to mucormycosis than others. Persons who have low amounts of neutrophils (neutropenia), which are white blood cells that help fight infection, and are taking broad-spectrum antibiotics, as well as people who are taking medicines that decrease the immune system's functioning, are at risk (immunosuppressive drugs). Neutropenia can be seen in and immunosuppressive drugs can be taken over for cancer, particularly blood (hematologic) cancers.

Mucormycosis is a fungal infection that affects persons who have recently had a hematopoietic stem cell transplant (HSCT). Hematopoietic stem cells are cells that grow into red blood cells, white blood cells, and platelets and are present in the bone marrow. The current bone marrow is removed and replaced with bone marrow from a healthy donor during a transplant. Immunosuppressive medications must be taken by infected people to help them fight rejection, but this can make them more vulnerable to infection, including HIV. People who get immunosuppressive medicines for other reasons, such as an organ transplant, are also at risk of contracting this illness. Some diabetics are at risk of acquiring mucormycosis, particularly if their diabetes is poorly managed and they develop diabetic ketoacidosis. Ketoacidosis is a diabetic condition in which the body produces high quantities of blood acids called ketones. Ketoacidosis can manifest itself in a variety of ways. The exact reasons why people with poorly controlled diabetes are more prone to mucormycosis are unknown, however it could be because these patients have more iron in their tissues. Mucormycosis is also a concern for those who have too much iron in their bodies (iron overload), which can occur as a result of frequent blood transfusions or certain blood illnesses. Researchers believe that these moulds can develop and spread by utilising the extra iron. Mucormycosis infection can use a medicine called deferoxamine, which is used to get rid of excess iron in the body, to get iron from the sick person. The usage of dextroamphetamine promotes infection growth and dissemination, making it another risk factor for mucormycosis infection. Other factors that increase the risk of developing mucormycosis include kidney failure, HIV/AIDS, the use of contaminated medical equipment near or in open wounds, long-term use of corticosteroids, which are extremely powerful anti-inflammatory medications, skin trauma such as burns or other skin injuries, extreme malnutrition, and illegal drug use involving needles. Immature neonates are more susceptible to infection, particularly mucormycosis. Some patients get mucormycosis without having any recognised risk factors, which happens seldom. Mucormycosis infection has a strong affinity for blood arteries, according to researchers. This suggests that the illness frequently affects blood vessels, however researchers aren't sure why. Infection of blood arteries can reduce blood flow, depriving tissues of oxygen and resulting in tissue death (necrosis).

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

A sinus infection (sinusitis) is the most common symptom, which is accompanied by nasal congestion, nasal discharge, and sinus pain. It's also possible to get a temperature and a headache. If the infection spreads beyond the sinuses, symptoms may include disintegration of the septum, a thin cartilage and bone wall that divides the nostrils, tissue loss (necrosis) of the palate, swelling of the area around the nose (perinasal area), and redness (erythema) of the skin overlying the sinus and the eye socket (orbit). Due to a lack of oxygen, there is often a blue-colored discoloration of the skin near the sinuses or the eye socket (cyanosis). Blurry vision or double vision might occur at times. If left untreated, substantial tissue death (necrosis) and infection can occur, causing considerable damage to facial features. Mucormycosis can sometimes extend to the brain. This might result in lethargy, impaired speech, seizures, partial paralysis, cranial neuropathies (abnormalities of the nerves of the face and eyes), a brain abscess, altered consciousness, and coma. This infection is known as rhinocerebral mucormycosis when it affects the sinuses and brain. When an infection spreads to the eye, it can cause swelling (periorbital edema), bulging or displacement of the eye (proptosis), visual loss, and maybe blindness owing to fluid buildup near to the eyes. Ophthalmoplegia is a condition in which the muscles that move the eyes are paralysed or weak, making it difficult or painful to move the eyes. Mucormycosis can cause pulmonary mucormycosis, which occurs when spores are breathed in and spread throughout the respiratory system. Pulmonary mucormycosis is a fast-progressing infection that is characterised by fever and a cough that produces no mucus (nonproductive cough). Chest pain, spitting or coughing up blood (hemoptysis), and difficulty breathing (dyspnea) are less common symptoms.

When mucormycosis affects the skin (cutaneous zygomycosis), patients can develop a single, painful, hardened region of skin as well as underlying tissue inflammation. The skin around you may become reddish, heated, swollen, and uncomfortable.

Open sores (ulcers) and blisters can develop, and tissue loss (necrosis) can occur, resulting in the affected tissue turning black. A fever is possible in those who are afflicted. Cutaneous mucormycosis can be mild or severe, with a rapid start (fulminant). The gastrointestinal system might be affected in some cases. This is most likely caused by spores being swallowed, inhaled into the mouth, or eating infected food.

Symptoms include stomach pain and blood vomiting (hematemesis). Lesions can form in the stomach or intestines, causing a hole to appear (perforation). Peritoneum infection (peritonitis) is an infection of the membrane that borders the abdominal wall and covers the organs inside the abdomen. Due to a lack of blood flow (bowel infarction), acute discomfort in the intestines can occur, and affected persons may fall into shock as a result of massive blood loss (hemorrhagic shock). Disseminated mucormycosis is a rare type of mucormycosis that affects people with weakened immune systems. In this state, the infection has migrated to other parts of the body and has the potential to become widespread (disseminated). The brain, spleen, skin, heart, and other organs are among the numerous organs that can be impacted. Mucormycosis can impact or spread to the kidneys, the inner lining of the heart chambers and heart valves (endocarditis), and the bone in rare cases (osteomyelitis). The signs and symptoms of disseminated mucormycosis vary a lot depending on which organ system is affected.

Most common symptoms observed are -

- ✦ Pain in face
- ✦ Cheek swelling
- ✦ Eye swelling
- ✦ Loss of Vision
- ✦ Stuffy nose
- ✦ Brownish/Bloody Nasal Discharge
- ✦ Dental pain
- ✦ Ulcer on palate
- ✦ Loosening of Teeth
- ✦ Swelling on Palate
- ✦ Headache

DIAGNOSIS

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS

A strong index of suspicion, identification of host variables, and timely assessment of clinical symptoms are all required for the diagnosis of mucormycosis. Diplopia in a patient with diabetes or pleuritic discomfort in a neutropenic host could be signs of infection, prompting the use of imaging modalities and the following collection of samples for microbiology, histology, and advanced molecular testing. Mucorales infection most commonly manifests as rhinocerebral, soft tissue, pulmonary, and disseminated disease, but it can affect practically any organ. Mucormycosis is characterised by tissue necrosis, however a diagnosis based on representation and syndromes lacks sensitivity and specificity. Other fungus, such *Aspergillus* or *Fusarium*, can cause the same symptoms.

Furthermore, in tuberculosis-endemic nations, the two illnesses may coexist, as in the case of a diabetic patient. There are, however, several characteristics that should raise your suspicion of invasive pulmonary mucormycosis. A history of past prophylaxis with voriconazole or the appearance of breakthrough fungal infection in an immunocompromised patient receiving antifungal medications active against *Aspergillus* but not Mucorales are examples of these. *Corzo-Leon et al.* proposed a diagnostic method for diabetic patients with rhinocerebral mucormycosis. Signs and symptoms that can be considered "red flags" include cranial nerve palsy, sinus pain, diplopia, periorbital edoema, proptosis, orbital apex syndrome, and palate ulcers. Mucormycosis is said to be more common in radiological terms, with numerous nodules and pleural effusion. The reverse halo sign is another finding on a computed tomography (CT) scan that appears to suggest the presence of mucormycosis (RHS). The RHS was detected in 15 of 16 patients (94 percent) during the first week of the disease in a recent investigation of consecutive thoracic CT scans in leukemic patients with neutropenia. Other radiologic abnormalities, such as numerous nodules, were detected later. The presence of the RHS on CT was a strong predictor of pulmonary mucormycosis in neutropenic leukemic individuals with lung infection, according to the source. Patients with mucormycosis had a higher RHS (54%) than those with aspergillosis (6%, P.001), while aspergillosis patients had more airway-invasive characteristics such as clusters of peribronchial consolidations, centrilobular nodules, and bronchial wall thickening. While these results aren't conclusive, they can be utilised as a starting point for more aggressive diagnostic laboratory procedures. PET/CT with is another emergent imaging tool that may potentially aid in the diagnosis and therapy of mucormycosis. Fluorodeoxyglucose is a kind of fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG). When feasible, endobronchial ultrasound-guided fine needle aspiration is also a useful diagnostic tool. [82-89]

MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATION AND CULTURE

The cornerstones of diagnosing mucormycosis are microscopy (direct and histopathological) and culture of various clinical specimens. Direct microscopy of clinical specimens, in combination with optical brighteners such as Blankophor and Calcofluor White, provides for a rapid presumptive diagnosis of mucormycosis. Mucorales hyphae range in width from 6 to 25 metres, are nonseptate or pauci-septate, and have an uneven, ribbon-like appearance. The branching angle is varied, including wide-angle (90) bifurcations. The distinction between hyphae of *Aspergillus* or morphologically related fungi and hyphae of Mucorales may not always be valid based on histopathological analysis of tissue specimens. Tissue identification, on the other hand, is a critical diagnostic technique since it distinguishes the existence of the fungus as a pathogen in the collection from a culture contaminant. On virtually fungal culture media, such as Sabouraud agar and potato dextrose agar cultured at 25°C to 30°C, all Mucorales grow quickly (3–7 days). A microaerophilic environment improves culture yield for some species. Surprisingly, even when fungal hyphae are visible in histopathologic study, only 50% of fungal cultures are positive. Because hyphae are brittle, they can be destroyed during tissue manipulation (avoidance of excessive tissue homogenization is recommended). For immunohistochemistry examination, a particular mouse monoclonal anti-Rhizomucor antibody was used nevertheless, this test has already been found to react with different Mucorales and Entomophthorales. *In situ* hybridization targeting 5S and 18S ribosomal RNA sequences⁴⁰ is still being researched. [90-99]

SPECIFIC IDENTIFICATION AND FUNGAL SUSCEPTIBILITY TESTING.

Identification of species is important for a better epidemiological understanding of mucormycosis and could be useful in epidemic investigations. On cultivation, Mucorales fungus are easily recognised from *Aspergillus* fungus. *Alvarez et al.* revealed that morphological functions alone can give a high level of accuracy when assessed by those with experience in fungal evidence. Identification of morphological taxonomic groups, on the other hand, is challenging and may be linked to speciation failures.⁴² ID32C kit (bio Merieux, *Marcy l'Etoile*, France) has been successfully used to identify *Lichtheimia corymbifera* and *R. pusillus*, while API 50CH (bioMerieux) has been used to identify Mucor species. Both tests failed to distinguish *M. circinelloides* and *M. rouxii*. *L. ramosa* is detected using ID32C and positive melezitose assimilation. MALDITOF mass spectrometry (matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionisation time-of-flight) is a promising method, however it is not yet valid for all Mucorales. The use of molecular-based tests concentrating on the internal transcribed spacer region is another reliable method. *M. circinelloides* has a high minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) in the presence of posaconazole, while *Rhizopus* and *Cunninghamella* have a high MIC in the presence of amphotericin B. The MIC of several *Apophysomyces* isolates against amphotericin B has also increased. The role of such data is unclear for patient treatment but needs to be later analyzed. [100-106]

SEROLOGY

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays, immunodiffusion tests, and immunoblots have all been tried with varying degrees of success. An enzyme-linked immunospot (ELISpot) assay was used to identify Mucorales specific T cells in three haematological patients who had developed invasive mucormycosis. Mucorales-specific T cells were never seen in any of the controls. Later research will look into the usage of such unique T cells as surrogate diagnostic markers. [107-110]

MOLECULAR ASSAY

Conventional polymerase chain reaction (PCR), restriction fragment length polymorphism examination (RFLP), DNA sequencing of defined gene regions, and melt curve analysis of PCR products are all examples of molecularbased tests. All of the above assays can be used to detect Mucorales signals or to identify them. The internal transcribed spacer or the 18S rRNA genes are the targets of the vast majority of molecular experiments. Various studies have been conducted utilising formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded, or fresh tissue samples³⁹, with varying results.

The investigations conducted have different degrees of sensitivity (70–100%) and specificity (not estimated to 100%), with the superior drawback being the small number of patients analysed. Because the efficacy of these inhouse tests has not been properly investigated and clinically evaluated, they cannot be recommended as a standalone, single strategy in clinical routine diagnostics. Recent attempts to diagnose diseases using molecular markers in blood and serum have generated promising clinical results. When compared to culture, molecularbased identification from serum resulted in earlier diagnosis and overall confirmed culture-proven instances. Currently, molecular-based diagnostic assays can be suggested as valuable add on tools that complement conventional diagnostic procedures. [98],[101],[102],[108-120]

TREATMENT

Treatment must address the patient's fundamental medical issue and reduce immunosuppression. Diabetics may have a better chance of succeeding than non-diabetics. *Yohai et al.* reported a coverall survival rate of 77 percent in diabetics and 34 percent in nondiabetics for rhino-orbito-cerebral mucormycosis. In patients with rhino-orbitocerebral mucormycosis, it is found that diabetics had a 60% survival rate and nondiabetics had a 20% survival rate. Those with serious illnesses, such as leukaemia and lymphoma, have a poor prognosis. With a combined surgical and medical therapy, the death rate for isolated pulmonary mucormycosis ranges from 9.4 to 27 percent, compared to 50–55 percent for patients treated just medically. In reported instances and candidates for different types of therapy, there is inherent selection bias. Antifungal therapy with an amphotericin B preparation, surgery and, if possible, repair of the underlying medical condition are the cornerstones of treatment. The only fungicidal agent with substantial *in-vitro* efficacy against *Zygomycetes* is amphotericin B. Mucorales are resistant to caspofungin and 5-flucytosine *in vitro*. Mucormycosis has been successfully treated with amphotericin B and its lipid formulations. Amphotericin B susceptibility varies between Mucorales species. The mean inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of *Cunninghamella* clinical isolates range from 1 lg mL to 100 lg mL. They primarily described a case of *C. bertholletiae* infection in an allogeneic bone marrow transplant patient who was unresponsive to two distinct forms of amphotericin B lipid formulations (amphotericin B liposomal and lipid complex). According to the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS) recommendations, the MIC was 4 lg mL. After receiving more than 10 g of liposomal amphotericin, amphotericin B lung concentrations from surgically detained tissue averaged 9.5 lg mL. Because of thrombosis and tissue infarction, amphotericin B levels at the site of involvement may not be enough. Itraconazole and Fluconazole have been used to treat mucormycosis in anecdotal case reports.

A 29-year-old woman with acute myelogenous leukaemia and pulmonary mucormycosis responded to fluconazole clinically and radiographically. Despite this, the reaction could have been a result of a recovering neutrophil count. Azole effectiveness has been proven to be poor in most *in vitro* and animal experiments. In guinea pig and murine models, azoles were ineffective against *Rhizopus* infection in mouse models of disseminated *Absidia* and *Rhizopus* infection, Itraconazole was mainly inferior to amphotericin B. Fluconazole in combination with trovafloxacin or Ciprofloxacin has been shown to be effective in the treatment of pulmonary mucormycosis in experimental mice. *In vitro*, voriconazole has little antimicrobial action against Mucorales. Posaconazole, a novel triazole in development, offers promise as a viable alternative to Mucorales. As seen by a rare instance of reported cavitary pulmonary mucormycosis caused by *Rhizopus* sp. that resolved without antifungal therapy after diabetic ketoacidosis was corrected, the underlying condition must be corrected for successful therapy.

To cure mucormycosis, a multimodal approach is required. Antifungal medicines must be given early, and metabolic imbalances must be corrected quickly. For diabetic people, sodium bicarbonate (together with insulin) can restore ketoacidosis, regardless of how severe the acidosis is. This can also stop Mucorales from invading hosts. Drugs like corticosteroids should aid in early diagnosis and tissue invasion prevention. Mucormycosis exhibits characteristics similar to thrombosis and tissue necrosis in a vase angio artery. A lipid formulation of amphotericin B has been proposed at a European conference as a solution to such a violent invasion. For injection into the central nervous system, the recommended dose is 5mg/kg/day up to 10mg/kg/day. The response rate for individuals with mucormycosis ranged from 78 percent in week one to 87 percent in week 12. Salvage treatment, which combines the effects of liquid amphotericin B with caspofungin or posaconazole, has shown to improve survival rates in individuals with rhino orbital cerebral mucormycosis. The use of hyperbaric oxygen to enhance the cytokine environment in order to reduce fungal cell area is effective in a high proportion of cases. This oxygen aids in the simulation of a granulocyte-macrophage colony, allowing for the production of interferon gamma to combat Mucorales. The drug VT-1161, a fungus inhibitor with selective activity, can be used for the final treatment. They suppress ergosterol formation and are a useful tool in the fight against mucormycosis. [121-136]

DRUGS USED IN TREATMENT

Sr.No.	Class of Drugs	Drugs
1.	Amphotericin-B	Liposomal Lyophilised Lipid Emulsion Deoxycholate Sonication
2.	Isavuconazole	
3.	Posaconazole	

Urgent Surgical debridement and strict glycemic control.

Inj. Amphoterecin B (1.0-1.5 mg/kg/day) or Inj. Amphoterecin B 5-10 mg/kg/day)

Intracranial Involvement (10mg/kg/day) OR Inj. Amphoterecin B lipid Complex (5mg/kg/day)

PRINCIPLE IN MANAGEMENT OF MUCORMYCOSIS

1. Early diagnosis
2. Early Surgery with Wide excision
3. Maximum Medical Management
4. Management of Complications (especially of Medical Management)
5. Team Approach [ENT + Ophthalmologist + Anaesthetist+ Physician + Infectious Disease Specialist + Endocrinologist + GI Medicine + Nephrologist + Neurologist + Neurosurgeon + Dentist + Psychiatrist]

MUCORMYCOSIS IN COVID-19

The severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2)-caused Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID19) has been linked to a variety of opportunistic bacterial and fungal diseases. The predominant fungal pathogens for co-infection in persons with COVID-19 have been identified as *Candida* and *Aspergillus*. Recently, multiple occurrences of mucormycosis in COVID19 patients have been recorded around the world, particularly in India. The capital reason that seems to be assisting Mucorales spores to germinate in people with COVID-19 is an perfect environment of low oxygen (hypoxia), steroid-induced hyperglycemia, acidic medium (metabolic acidosis, diabetic ketoacidosis [DKA]), high iron levels (increased ferritins), high glucose (diabetes), new-onset hyperglycemia, and decreased phagocytic activity of white blood cells (WBC) due to immunosuppression (SARSCoV-2) mediated, steroid-mediated or background comorbidities) coupled with various other shared risk factors including elongated hospitalization with or without mechanical ventilators.

Paltauf first identified Phycomycosis or Zygomycosis in 1885, which was later renamed Mucormycosis in 1957 by Baker, an American pathologist, for a belligerent *Rhizopus* infection. Mucormycosis is a rare but deadly fungal infection that mostly affects those with weakened immune systems. Mold fungi of the genus *Rhizopus*, *Rhizomucor*, *Mucor*, *Cunninghamella*, and *Absidia* of the Order Mucorales, Class Zygomycetes cause mucormycosis. The *Rhizopus Oryzae* is the most common form, accounting for approximately 60% of human mucormycosis cases, as well as *Journal*. 90% of the Rhino-orbital-cerebral (ROCM) form is pre-proofed. The inhalation of fungus spores is the mode of contamination. According to a recent projection for the year 2019-2020, the prevalence of mucormycosis ranged from 0.005 to 1.7 per million people worldwide, with a ratio approximately 80 times greater (0.14 per 1000) in India than in developed countries. To put it another way, India has the largest number of mucormycosis cases in the world. Despite this, India has the world's second-largest diabetes mellitus (DM) population and was, until recently, the world's diabetes hotspot. Importantly, in India, diabetes mellitus is the most prevalent risk factor for mucormycosis, whereas in Europe and the United States, haematological malignancies and organ transplant take the lead. DM, on the other hand, remains the leading risk factor for mucormycosis worldwide, with a fatality rate of 46%. While long-term use of corticosteroids has been linked to opportunistic fungal infections such as aspergillosis and mucormycosis, even a short course of corticosteroids has lately been linked to mucormycosis, particularly in persons with diabetes. Mucormycosis caused by even a short period (5–14 days) of steroid medication is uncommon, especially in patients with diabetes]. In the European Confederation of Medical Mycology research, 46 percent of the patients had received corticosteroids within one month of the diagnosis of mucormycosis. In patients with COVID-19, there has been an increase in case reports/series of mucormycosis, particularly in India. Several case reports have also been received from various parts of the world. When mucormycosis spreads to the brain, the mortality rate rises to as high as 90%. Furthermore, the pace with which mucormycosis spreads is a rare phenomena, and even a 12-hour delay in diagnosis can be lethal, which is why 50 percent of cases of zygomycosis have traditionally been detected only in post-mortem autopsy series.

MUCORMYCOSIS IN DIABETES MELLITUS PATIENT

- If people acquire symptoms of mucormycosis, they should see a doctor very away, especially diabetics (Black fungus infection).
- Patients get this illness either after recovering from COVID-19 or after testing positive for COVID-19. They all have one thing in common: they're diabetics.
- The coronavirus can affect the pancreas and cause blood sugar levels to fluctuate, either as a result of the disease or as a result of treatment.
- Sugar provides a favourable environment for mucormycosis to develop when the immune system of the body gets weakened, especially in uncontrolled diabetic patients with extremely high blood sugar levels. It's critical to maintain blood sugar levels under control both during and after therapy.
- Patients with diabetes must keep their blood sugar levels under control by taking medications as directed by their doctors, eating a balanced diet, and exercising regularly.
- Blood sugar levels must be checked on a daily basis. Whether or whether they have symptoms of mucormycosis, they should see a doctor if the level is high.
- Diabetics should be extremely cautious about following the safety precautions to avoid contracting COVID-19.

CONCLUSION

Mucormycosis is becoming more common in people with weakened immune systems, and the fatality rate from current treatment remains unacceptably high. Although research into the pathophysiology of zygomycosis is still in its early stages, substantial breakthroughs have recently been made in understanding how Mucorales produces disease and lives in the host. The majority of the research has been on fungal iron uptake methods, molecular processes of adhesion/invasion, sex loci, spore size, and the involvement of innate and adaptive immunity in Mucorales host defence. The lack of interest from pharmaceutical corporations in a condition with a tiny market revenue opportunity is the biggest roadblock to turning novel technology into genuine therapeutics. As a result, federally sponsored research methods must back up newly promising treatment/diagnostic discoveries for unique diseases that pose a public health danger.

This study is being done in order to distribute information on Mucormycosis, as well as the signs and symptoms of the disease, in order to prevent it.

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List of Abbreviations-

ROCM : Rhinocerebral Mucormycosis

HIV : Human Immuno Deficiency virus

AIDS : Acquired Immuno Deficiency Syndrome

Conflict of interest

The author declares there's no conflict of interest.

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